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Project Summery

A biological compound was extracted from an exotic mushroom and investigated to cytotoxic activity. Ethanol, hot and cold water extracts of the mushroom species are screened for cytotoxic activity against healthy cancer cell lines and mammary gland adenocarcinoma cells (MDA-MB-231, MCF7 with validated vitro assay. The extracts from the mushroom demonstrated significant cytotoxic activity towards a range of cancer cell lines. The main objective of the study is to demonstrate complex and multilevel nature of mushroom anticancer potential. The exercise is based on different compound groups able to simultaneously target a range of biological processes relevant in the treatment of cancer and focuses on targeted approaches to specific malignant tissues. The study aims to show some aspects of biological compounds on tumors that have been studied to unlock areas for further studies. The study will also look into the types of cancers that can be susceptible to treatment by the biological compound.

Background

Mushrooms have been used in many civilizations all over the history of mankind in china, Africa, Latin America and Japan where they have been used as a rich nutrient source and part of medicinal regiments. There are over 7,000 edible mushroom species with around 800 known for their significant pharmacological properties and are referred to as medicinal mushrooms. Modern medical research on medicinal mushrooms has been ongoing for the last 60 years with many scientific articles published on the subject. Many properties of numerous species of mushrooms have been investigated as extracts of a whole fruiting body or mycelia or isolated active substances including polysaccharides and polysaccharide-protein complexes. Over one hundred and fifty therapeutic effects of various species of mushrooms are already resisted including antifungal, antioxidants, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, immunosuppressive, mitogenic, immunomodulatory, and hepatoprotective (Shamsaei et al, 2020). These effects of properties of mushrooms are attributed to high molecular weight metabolites including lectones, lipids, and polysaccharides as well as low molecular weight secondary metabolites range including lactones, alkaloids, terpenoids, sterols and phenolic substances. Secondary metabolites are derived from many intermediates in primary metabolite pathways and their main ecological adaptation is their variety and abundance. Such fungal secondary metabolites as cephalosporins and penicillin are used all over the world as antibiotics. Cancer as a complex disease group is known to alter molecular pathways in sequences. All the pathways can be modulated by certain medicinal mushroom species and medicinal mushroom compounds. Some compounds such as Polysaccharide peptide are known to reduce the

proliferation of MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells and increases p21WAF1/CIP1 and decreases the expression of cyclin D1.

Many studies on medicinal species of mushrooms have shown that they possess antitumor effects. These include blended extracts from mushrooms hypothesized to have superior biological properties as compared to simple extracts. There is no sufficient data to address anticancer effects of standardized medicinal mushroom blended extracts. This research proposal aims to determine the anticancer effects of a biological compound from an exotic mushroom from the Brazilian forest.

Methodology

MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 breast cancer cell lines were cultured in 7 different dishes and incubated for 8, 16, 24, 36, 48 and 60 hours and cell lysates from each dish were prepared and one dish was left as control at 0 hours. The cell lysates were then used to perform an in vitro kinase assay in order to measure the cyclin-dependent kinase. An antibody was then used to bind cyclin B protein with cdk1 to immunoprecipitate them and subject them to in vitro kinase assay under radioactive ATP. The results were then loaded to acrylamide gel and individual components separated and then exposed to a radioactive film. The results show kinase activity diminishing overtime in response to the treatment of UFC against breast cancer as it impinges their cell cycles. 5-bromo-2'-deoxyuridine labeling index was used in determining synthesis phase of cells. The death of cells in both monolayer and spheroid cultures was determined using Poly-ADP-ribose-polymerase immunohistochemical staining and terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick and labeling assay.

Figure: Real-time cell proliferation assay

Relevance

Medicinal mushrooms have over history of mankind been used in the treatment of many diseases including cancer. The present project proposal aims to study and reveal the chemical

nature and mechanism of action for biomedical capacity of mushrooms. The recent decades in medical research especially in cancer treatment have been marked by targeted cancer treatment that is not harmful to healthy tissues (Shamsaei et al, 2020). Fungal compounds extracted from mushrooms have shown the potential to be an innovational drug reservoir. Many studies have shown that biological compounds extracted from mushrooms inhibit experimentally induced malignancies of the colon, skin, liver, prostate and breast and promote the inhibition of cancer cell line proliferation. This research proposal proposes an intended study to investigate the effects of a biological compound extracted from mushrooms from the Brazilian forest on the human breast carcinoma cell lines MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7.

Pitfalls

The study will demonstrate how the extracted biological compound can be used to inhibit the growth of cancer. The scope of the research is based on the effects of extracts rather than the mushroom itself. It will be difficult to attribute the effects to either the mushroom or the extract.

References

Shamsaei, S., Getso, M., Ahmadikia, K., Yarahmadi, M., Farahani, H.E., Aslani, R., Mohammadzade, A.S., Raissi, V., Soleimani, A., Arghavan, B. and Karami, S., 2020. Recent findings on the role of fungal products in the treatment of cancer. *Clinical and Translational Oncology*, pp.1-8.